

Separation of Ni from multicomponent mixtures : Ni was separated from multicomponent mixtures by exploiting the difference in elution with HCl in the presence of different concentration of different kinds of non-aqueous solvents. It was possible to separate Ni from complex mixtures containing Zn, Pb, Cu, Fe, Mn, Bi, Cd, U and Th. The details of such separation are shown in Table 2.

The separation of Ni from Cu, Fe, Mn, Cd and Al is important as they are generally associated with one another in alloys. The isolation of Ni from Zr, Th, Ce, U and Ba has practical application. The overall operation for the separation and determination does not exceed 3 h. The results are reproducible.

References

1. F. W. E. STRELOW and O. H. S. W. WEINERT, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **83**, 179.
2. M. SIMEK and J. HANAK, *Scripta Ohem.*, 1971, **1**, 119.
3. F. W. E. STRELOW, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **113**, 823.
4. F. W. E. STRELOW, A. H. VICTOR, J. STEYN and H. H. LACHMANN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 173.
5. F. W. E. STRELOW, O. H. S. W. WEINERT and T. N. N. WALT, *Talanta*, 1974, **21**, 1183.
6. A. G. GAIKWAD and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 905.

Aas Determination of Tin in various Samples after Extraction with Liquid Anion-exchanger

SUPRA BANDYOPADHYAY and ARABINDA K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, Burdwan University,
Burdwan-713 104

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VARIOUS carboxylates of tin(II) compounds have been reported¹. The present communication reports the extraction behaviour of tin as $\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})_2^{2-}$ with liquid anion-exchanger, Aliquat 336, in benzene. The determination of tin have been carried out by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (aas).

Experimental

Aliquat 336 (Fluka, A.G.) liquid anion-exchanger was used without further purification. A stock solution of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) was prepared and the solution was standardised² before use. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. A Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer with a tin hollow cathode lamp was used, and the conditions were optimised according to its manual. The pH values were measured with a Systronics 331 expanded pH meter.

The general procedure was based upon solvent extraction technique. The aqueous phase was made up from a 5.0 ml of the solution containing 237.38

μg of tin ; 0.05 M oxalic acid solution (2.0 ml) was added, pH of the resulting solution adjusted to 2.3 and finally phthalate-buffer (1.5 ml) added. Then the aqueous phase was made up to 10 ml and was equilibrated in a separatory funnel with 5% (v/v) Aliquat 336 in benzene (10 ml) for 5 min. The two layers were allowed to settle for 10 min. The organic phase was then separated carefully to another separatory funnel. In order to remove the organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with benzene (5 ml). The resulting extract was mixed with the earlier separated organic phase. Then 2 M HNO_3 (10 ml) was added to the organic phase and the mixture was shaken for 5 min. The two phases were allowed to settle. The aqueous phase was carefully separated and again washed with benzene (5 ml) to remove any entrained solvent present in the separated aqueous phase. The amount of tin extracted was estimated by aas in presence of 1000-fold excess NaNO_3 , which enhanced the tin absorption by about 20%³.

Results and Discussion

Extraction of tin complex became quantitative in the pH range 2.0-2.6. Quantitative extraction of tin occurs with benzene (97.3%), and extractions with other solvents show 94.6% in carbon disulphide, 91.9% in toluene, 83.8% in nitrobenzene, 75.7% in 1,2-dichloroethane, 70.3% in isobutyl methyl ketone, 59.5% in amyl alcohol and 35.1% in chloroform. It was found that the extraction increased with increasing extractant concentration and was complete at 5% Aliquat 336. The extraction time was quantitative within 2 min and stripping complete within 3 min, and it was maintained 5 min in both the cases. For the determination of tin, tolerance limits (within an error of $\pm 2\%$) for various ions are as follows : Al^{III} , Cr^{III} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} (all 40-fold) ; Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , sulphate (all 80-fold) ; Fe^{III} , phosphate (all 12-fold).

The extraction of $\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})_2^{2-}$ is quantitative provided the Aliquat 336-tin mole ratio is ≥ 2 . Plot of log D against log [Aliquat 336] provides a straight line with slope around 2. Thus the simple extraction mechanism of Sn^{II} may be represented as

where, o = organic phase and a = aqueous phase.

Analyses of tin in different samples : Several samples were analysed for tin contents after decomposition by the standard methods (Table 1). Solder, a certified sample (59.9% Sn), was decomposed⁴ and

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TIN IN VARIOUS SAMPLES

Sample	Amount taken g	Sn found* mg g ⁻¹	Standard deviation
Solder	0.101 00	594.658	± 0.043
Toothpaste	3.344 08	0.161	± 0.011
Vegetable oil	9.558 20	0.016	± 0.002

* Average of 4 determinations

analysed to check the present method. In tooth-pastes, fluoride is usually added as its tin salt (SnF_2). With this end in view a fluoride-toothpaste (Hindustan Ciba-Geigy) was decomposed⁵ and analysed by the proposed method. Vanaspati (hydrogenated fat) is commonly available in a tinned can. In an ordinary groceteria, it is stored in the old tinned can for long time and may be contaminated with metallic tin. Such Vanaspati (Hindusthan Lever) sample was decomposed⁶ and analysed by the present method.

References

1. J. D. DONALDSON and A. JELLEN, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1968, 1448, 2244.
2. J. BASSETT, R. O. DENNEY, G. H. JEFFERY and J. MENDHAM, "Vogel's Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Chemistry including Elementary Instrumental Analysis", 4th. ed., ELBS, London, 1978, p. 889.
3. E. J. AGAZZI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, 37, 864.
4. F. D. SNELL, C. T. SNELL, and C. A. SNELL, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis including Photometric Methods", Van Nostrand, Princeton, 1959, Volume IIA, p. 130.
5. "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", ed. N. H. FURMAN, 6th. ed., Van Nostrand, Princeton, 1962, Vol. I, p. 1087.
6. "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", ed. F. J. WELCHER, 6th. ed., Van Nostrand, Princeton, 1962, Vol. II, Part B, p. 1422.